

COVID 19 – An Environmental Pandemic!

By

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Corona Virus, Epidemic , Pandemic , Immunity , Anti-oxidant , Acyclovir , Flavipiravir , Isolation , Social Distancing , Sepsis

Corona Virus – A Spasmo-demic (Non dictionary term) ! . Spasmodic + Epidemic – used here. Spasmodic w.r.t our environment. A critical Virological pathogen throughout the World is destroying the environmental sustainability increasing the Death rate every Day . The COVID19 is the latest model is one of the greatest headache to World Health Organisation (WHO) , Environmental Protection agency (EPA) .

We are all aware of the following facts :

- ✓ The Genetic recombination of the Virus .
- ✓ Very High Mutation Capacity.
- ✓ Pneumonia / Lungs attack – Virulent to Death .
- ✓ Isolation of the patient under HEPA filter (Hospital Pharmacy Sch) .
- ✓ Social distancing / Separation.
- ✓ Disinfectant Washing of Hands (WHO & EPA) .
- ✓ Use of N95 or Equivalent mask , Hand Gloves .
- ✓ Natural Immunity Booster like Anti-Oxidant therapy, Balanced, Protein diet.
- ✓ Use of Drugs like **Hydroxy Chloroquine (HChQ)** , & Acyclovir higher generation analogue.
- ✓ FLAVIPIRAVIR – The Drug development at China .
- ✓ Virological Mathematical modelling is required .

- ✓ LOCK DOWN & National Disaster Management Acts .

FULL TEXT REF :

1. https://www.researchgate.net/post/Let_us_Discuss_something_about_Reproducibl_e_research_technique_including_COVID_19
2. https://www.researchgate.net/post/Whether_Bio-Technological_Research_is_essential_to_develope_our_nation_including_the_threa_ts_of_Corona_Virus-How
3. https://www.researchgate.net/post/Whether_Chemistry_Pharmacy_are_interdiscip_linary-Academics_research
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5. https://www.researchgate.net/post/What_do_you_prefer_to_take_ANIMAL_or_VEGETABLE_protein_under_attack_of_corona_virus
6. https://www.researchgate.net/post/How_Drugless_therapy_helps_us_to_Improve_our_health_as_well_as_to_prevent_Viral_attack
7. https://www.researchgate.net/post/Your_favourite_food_as_Anti-Oxidant-Let_us_discuss

8 . BIO-TECHNOLOGY: Newer Biology -An Impression - DOI 10.17605/OSF.IO/CZSB9

In this Impression a modern scope of bio-technology is discussed. The word Bio-Technology literally means a combinatorial hybrid of classical Biological - science with some Chemical Industrial aspects. The micro biomes – the origin of this newer biology ie MICROBIOLOGY , MOLECULAR BIOLOGY .